

AN INVESTIGATION OF PRECISION & BIAS IN TENSION SPECIMEN CONFIGURATIONS

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes the results of an experimental investigation to determine the relative precision and bias in strength and modulus determination using four different tension specimens. The study used a conventional, 120 °C cure, woven fiberglass / epoxy material. The specimen configurations studied were dog bone configurations ASTM D638 types I and II, straight-sided ASTM D3039, and a constant radius (CR) reduced section specimen being investigated by one of the authors as a candidate to replace tab bonded specimens in composite material specifications.

The experimental program consisted of 5 replicate tests of each configuration. The influence of specimen misalignment was investigated at 0, 1 and 3 degrees. The reduced section configurations were significantly more sensitive to misalignment than a straight sided specimen. The interaction of elevated temperature and misalignment (70 °C and 1 degree) was also evaluated and was found to correlate with the abruptness of change in specimen cross section. All the data, a total of 80 individual tests, are included in the paper.

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials have developed a reputation for exhibiting high scatter in properties which in many cases is completely unjustified. The apparent "scatter" is usually due to problems with specimen fabrication, testing, or by comparing data from methods with significant biases. The most common sources of test bias are specimen fabrication quality (including tabbing material choices), and stress concentrations inherent to the specimen design or geometry.

Efforts of the authors to develop a simple robust specimen configuration led to the evaluation of the constant radius (CR) specimen of Fig 1. This configuration evolved from a set of design constraints which were considered essential for a robust, accurate test method suitable for inclusion in a materials specification. A tabless design would eliminate all the quality problems and biases associated with bonded tabs. Current ASTM D30 Committee studies have found

significant bias in D3039 tension results due to tab bonding parameters and procedures, especially with high modulus adhesives. The CR specimen is simple to machine, has a low stress concentration factor and can be used both in tension and compression with conventional methods of buckling stabilization.

The CR specimen was extensively evaluated on carbon / epoxy materials with excellent results [1-3]. It was decided to see how well this configuration performed with a more conventional woven fiberglass / epoxy material and to compare it to existing test methods in common usage.

Figure 1. Constant Radius Specimen Configuration

EXPERIMENTAL PLAN

The most commonly used tension test methods for composite materials are ASTM D638 for fiberglass materials and ASTM D3039 for composites with high modulus fibers such as carbon or boron. The test matrix shown in Table 1, was performed to compare these methods and the CR specimen. The relative sensitivity of the methods to off-axis machining was also included in the experimental plan. Off-axis machining of specimens with respect to fiber orientation is a common source of data scatter .

Table 1. Experimental Plan

Off Axis Angle (degrees)	0	1	3	1
Test Temperature (deg. C)	22	22	22	71
ASTM D3039	5	5	5	5
ASTM D638 Type I	5	5	5	5
ASTM D638 Type II	5	5	5	5
Constant Radius	5	5	5	5

Total of 80 specimens

SPECIMEN PREPARATION

All of the test specimens were machined from a single laminated panel. The panel was autoclave cured at 120 °C in accordance with the Boeing process specification for the material. The panel consisted of 12 plies of style 1581 E-glass prepreg with all plies oriented in the same direction. All of the specimens were cut parallel to the fabric warp direction. Conventional tab bonding and machining procedures were followed.

The panel cutting diagram is presented in Fig. 2. Special procedures were developed to assure all specimens were made identically with the exact measure of axial misalignment specified in the experimental plan. Similar care was exercised in specimen testing. With this level of control in making the specimens, any differences in results could be directly attributed to the test methods.

Fig 2. Panel Cutting Diagram

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Since only a brief discussion can be included in this paper, a complete tabulation of test results is presented at the end of this paper for any subsequent analyses readers may wish to perform

The first observation made was that all of the individual test series (5 specimen replicates), exhibited essentially the same variability. The average coefficient of variation (COV) observed was around 2.3% for strength and modulus. This level of variation was expected since stable and identical processes were used throughout the experimental program. Individual results are summarized in Fig 2.

The next observation made is related to failure mode. It is difficult to determine the accuracy of mechanical tests since the true material property is never known. An improper failure mode or location can be considered a strong indicator that test results may be suspect (biased). Distinct differences in failure modes between the methods were observed. Both the D3039 and D638-Type I specimens tested at room temperature failed either at the tab or at the radius transition region except at elevated temperatures where failures were generally in the gage section. The D638-Type II and CR specimens consistently failed in the gage section.

Figure 3. Test Method Strength Precision Comparison

STRENGTH BIAS Differences (bias) in test results between various test methods or laboratories can usually be attributed to one of the following:

1. Specimen quality.
2. Testing equipment or procedures.
3. Varying stress concentration factors inherent to specimen design.
4. Different test specimen volumes.

The first two sources of bias were eliminated by the controlled nature of the experimental plan leaving only stress concentration factors (SCF) and test volumes to be considered, which was the objective of this study.

The constant radius specimen has an intentionally low stress concentration factor. The radius (large) and reduction in cross-section area (small) were picked to just compensate for stress concentrations due to specimen gripping. It was believed this approach would yield the best estimate of true material properties. The stress concentrations for the D3039 and D638 were reported to be identical for both configurations [3] and equal to a value of 1.14.

The strengths from the D638 and D3039 specimens were essentially the same. The relatively small differences between the specimen configurations were consistent with the differences in specimen volume as predicted by a Weibull volume effect analysis using the equation:

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_1}{\sigma_2}\right) = \left(\frac{V_2}{V_1}\right)^{\frac{1}{\alpha}} \quad (1)$$

where α = Weibull shape parameter and $\sigma_{(i)}$, $V_{(i)}$ = strength, volume of specimen (i). The shape parameter estimated from the average test COV of 2.3% gives a value of $\alpha = 55$ [4]. The predicted strength ratio between the largest (D3039) and the smallest specimen (D638/II) was 1.039. The experimentally determined ratio averaged 1.042. The statistical uncertainty in all averages is $\pm 2\%$ based on a sample size of 5 and a COV of 2.3%. The higher mean strengths obtained with the CR specimen are therefore attributed to its low SCF.

The interaction effect of fiber misalignment and temperature on strength was significantly greater for the reduced section specimens than the tab-bonded straight sided D3039 specimen. The influence of this effect was found to correlate with the abruptness of change in specimen cross

section (Fig 4). Reducing the specimen cross section results in cut fibers, discontinuous between the grips. The load in these fibers must be transferred to continuous fibers by shear through the resin. Elevated temperature reduces the shear stiffness of the resin and its ability to transfer load.

Figure 4. Temperature- Alignment Interactions

MODULUS All of the specimens were tested with an extensometer in order to determine modulus. Modulus was calculated using both a chord method (1000 - 6000 μ strain) and by a least-squares-fit (LSF) of the linear portion in the load-strain recordings. All of the methods gave consistent results with low variation.

The average COV in modulus was 2.3% for both the chord method and the LSF method. The maximum difference in average modulus among the four methods investigated was 3.1% for the chord method and 2.2% for the LSF method. The LSF method produced a consistent 10% higher modulus than the chord method (Fig 5). The factor will vary with selection of chord points.

The LSF modulus is in essence a mathematical way of calculating the steepest portion of the load-strain curve. The actual algorithm sequentially calculates the sliding tangent modulus and analyzes if it varies by a specific amount from an initially calculated guess at the steepest portion of the curve. The actual LSF modulus is then smoothed over the region deemed "straight" to within the given tolerances. The process is complicated by the necessity to account for the quantization of the digital data and the inherent lack of accuracy at the initial regions of data collection [6].

Figure 5. Chord / LSF Modulus Method Comparison

SUMMARY

An experimental program comparing three conventional test methods (ASTM D3039, ASTM D638 Type I, and Type II) with a constant radius (CR) test specimen indicated all of the methods had similar precision. The average coefficient of variation was found to be 2.3% for both strength and modulus.

The CR specimen produced significantly higher strengths than the other methods. This bias is consistent with differences in stress concentration factors between the specimens. If you agree with a commonly voiced criteria that 'the test specimen producing the highest result is the most accurate'; then the constant radius specimen is the most accurate and D3039 the least accurate.

The straight sided D3039 specimen was the least sensitive to fiber misalignment. The interaction of misalignment and temperature was found to correlate with the abruptness of change in specimen cross sectional area.

Modulus determination by either the chord or LSF method had the same precision and showed no bias between the test methods. The least squares method of calculating modulus produced a consistent 10% higher modulus.

REFERENCES

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6. ASTM D20 Plastics Working Group Document, Standard Guide for Interpretation of Computerized Stress-Strain Curves, Version 4, Oct. 91.

Appendix 1 : Test Results

Specimen Configuration	Nominal Angle (degrees)	Test Temp (deg C)	Tension Strength (MPa)	Chord Modulus (GPa)	LSF Modulus (GPa)
ASTM D3039	0	22	396	22.34	23.92
			392	21.17	23.17
			402	21.72	23.92
			410	21.65	23.37
			402	21.72	23.37
			Average	400	21.72
COV(%)	1.71	1.92	1.49		
ASTM D3039	1	22	389	20.68	22.61
			387	21.44	23.86
			380	21.51	24.27
			403	21.44	23.92
			380	21.24	23.37
			Average	388	21.26
COV(%)	2.48	1.60	2.71		
ASTM D3039	3	22	379	21.93	23.72
			378	21.03	22.82
			372	21.30	23.58
			365	21.58	23.92
			382	21.30	23.58
			Average	375	21.43
COV(%)	1.75	1.58	1.78		
ASTM D3039	1	71	379	19.10	21.58
			371	21.44	23.58
			304	16.41	18.89
			362	19.37	20.27
			356	18.96	21.03
			Average	354	19.06
COV(%)	8.33	9.39	8.20		
Constant Radius	0	22	487	22.68	25.10
			486	22.41	24.96
			463	21.86	24.27
			498	22.27	24.61
			472	22.41	24.55
			Average	481	22.33
COV(%)	2.82	1.35	1.34		
Constant Radius	1	22	472	21.30	23.86
			474	21.30	23.58
			468	21.37	23.92
			470	21.10	23.51
			467	21.58	24.34
			Average	470	21.33
COV(%)	0.57	0.81	1.38		
Constant Radius	3	22	436	20.55	23.44
			415	21.37	23.65
			440	20.48	23.24
			442	20.96	23.92
			427	20.62	23.44
			Average	432	20.79
COV(%)	2.54	1.79	1.11		
Constant Radius	1	71	407	19.31	21.79
			405	18.89	21.03
			418	19.10	21.10
			398	19.37	22.13
			401	19.86	21.65
			Average	406	19.31
COV(%)	1.87	1.87	2.18		

Appendix 1: Test Results (Cont.)

Specimen Configuration	Nominal Angle (degrees)	Test Temp (deg C)	Tension Strength (MPA)	Chord Modulus (GPA)	LSF Modulus (GPA)
ASTM 638-Type I	0	22	404	21.51	23.79
			416	21.86	23.86
			419	21.10	23.17
			427	21.44	23.37
			405	21.10	23.37
			Average COV(%)	414 2.36	21.40 1.49
ASTM 638-Type I	1	22	402	21.30	23.58
			403	20.48	22.55
			424	20.82	22.89
			410	20.68	22.82
			416	21.24	23.24
			Average COV(%)	411 2.25	20.90 1.70
ASTM 638-Type I	3	22	375	20.27	23.03
			357	19.99	22.48
			359	19.93	22.68
			366	20.20	22.34
			373	20.06	22.48
			Average COV(%)	366 2.23	20.09 0.71
ASTM 638-Type I	1	71	334	19.31	21.72
			331	20.96	22.75
			350	19.72	22.41
			345	18.96	21.37
			294	17.10	19.03
			Average COV(%)	331 6.55	19.21 7.29
ASTM 638-Type II	0	22	444	21.79	24.27
			411	21.65	23.79
			408	21.10	23.86
			404	21.37	23.86
			434	20.75	23.24
			Average COV(%)	420 4.19	21.33 1.96
ASTM 638-Type II	1	22	423	21.10	23.86
			416	21.17	23.79
			440	21.24	23.17
			434	21.30	23.24
			443	21.30	23.51
			Average COV(%)	431 2.60	21.22 0.42
ASTM 638-Type II	3	22	369	20.82	23.65
			402	20.75	22.75
			394	20.62	22.96
			392	20.48	23.37
			391	20.62	23.10
			Average COV(%)	389 3.16	20.66 0.65
ASTM 638-Type II	1	71	369	20.82	21.17
			402	20.75	20.89
			394	20.62	21.10
			392	20.48	20.62
			391	20.62	20.06
			Average COV(%)	389 3.16	20.66 0.65